

PROBLEMS OF ARTISTIC AND AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE THROUGH THE ART OF CHOREOGRAPHY

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Annotation. This article will consider the issue of aesthetic value and variability of the art of choreography in the process of the development of the younger generation.

Keywords: choreographic art, aesthetic education, folk dance, stylization.

Introduction. In the formation of the aesthetic and artistic culture of the individual, the images of the art of choreography are the most important aspect of aesthetic education. Choreography is a world of movement beauty, sounds, light colors, colorful costumes, that is, the world of magical art. And the choreographic image is a holistic expression of feelings and thoughts in dance, human character. A certain figurative dance is filled with meaningful, emotional, inner meaning. The art of choreography has always attracted the attention of children. This art became widespread in preschool institutions, secondary schools.

Today, under the leadership of our President, an active policy is being conducted in our country based on raising the spirit of patriotism, respect for our national traditions and values, forming a mentally and physically healthy generation, and protecting the rights and interests of young people.

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4585 of 04.02.2020 "On the fundamental improvement of the system of training highly qualified personnel in the field of dance art and measures to further develop the scientific potential", the State Academy of Choreography of Uzbekistan, the program of measures for the organization and improvement of activities of the republican specialized boarding school of choreography and primary boarding schools specialized in dance art was approved. Thus, in the following years, in our country, in terms of supporting and developing our ancient and rich cultural heritage, our national identity, our unique values and traditions, culture and art, based on the traditions of "Master-disciple". Systematic works are being carried out in order to organize dance schools, train specialists and highly qualified personnel according to international standards, and accelerate the development of science by effectively using the scientific potential in the field of dance art.

The era itself assumes the comprehensive development of the art of

Dance, which is important in raising the spirituality and aesthetic education of our people, widely introducing the noble generation to the samples of national and world dance art.

This ensures a more complete development of the individual abilities of children, so in choreographic groups, training should enter a wide range of children and adolescents. Young people love the art of dancing and participate in training for a long time, show perseverance and diligence in acquiring dance knowledge and skills. Teachers of choreography have the opportunity to carry out a lot of educational work using specific tools of dance art, taking into account the interest, diligence of children. Dance classes contribute to the aesthetic education of children, have a positive effect on their physical development, contribute to the growth of their general culture, so it can be noted that the art of choreography has a rich opportunity for the wide implementation of educational tasks. Children strive to see it in ballet performances, art albums, videos, get acquainted with the images of animated literary works in the choreographic works of great choreographers. Choreography Sana'ti is the practice of physical development and spiritual nourishment.

Engaged in the art of dance, the child is characterized by holding his torso, everyone around him looks with enthusiasm, but his formation is a long process that requires many qualities from children. Discipline, hard work and patience, character traits necessary not only in the choreographic lesson, but also in everyday life. These qualities have been cultivated over the years by the leaders of choreographic groups and Mark success in many works. The feeling of responsibility, which is so necessary in life, moves children who are engaged in choreography forward. It is impossible to make even more responsibility in public dance darcor, delay, oblivion, because the performance of those around you depends on you, not to learn, not to do, not to work on oneself will overtake not only the performer himself, but the whole group. Discipline in the group, a sense of responsibility, the fact that training clothes should be clean, even in a comprehensive school, affect the appearance and behavior of children. They are distinguished not only by their posture, but also by their hairstyle, cleanliness and elegance in wearing the simplest clothes. [1]

The art of choreography is an addition and continuation of the real life of the child, enriching it. Learning this art brings such feelings and experiences to the child that he cannot find these from other sources. Educational work in the artistic team, a complex, lush process. This is due to the implementation of an

extensive program of organizational-pedagogical and artistic-executive measures. Each direction in the practice of the leader has its own internal logic, its own laws and principles of implementation. Without their knowledge, without critical analysis, it is impossible to adequately effectively organize not only artistic-creative, educational, educational and training activities, but also the provision of the entire pedagogical process. [2] the specificity of educational work in the choreographic community is associated with an organic combination of artistic, performing, general pedagogical and social aspects in its implementation and provision. The efforts of the leader are aimed at the formation of a worldview in children, the upbringing of a high moral culture, artistic and aesthetic development. These tasks are solved by involving children in artistic and performing activities, organizing educational and creative work. So, the first level of raising a child in a choreographic team is the formation of a child as a person, the development of civic, moral and aesthetic qualities in him, a common culture. Parents send their children to choreographic circles, which are a means of improving health, expanding the overall cultural-artistic worldview, a form of satisfaction of spiritual needs, the development of aesthetic taste. Therefore, the attitude of children to classes is selected individually and strictly. The child perceives, remembers and performs what interests him, attracts him. Educational work should be carried out systematically, only then will it bring positive results [1].

The complexity of educational work is determined by the fact that children in the team meet at different levels of culture and upbringing. Sometimes it is not easy to direct their interests. At the same time, the teacher-leader should show politeness, sensitivity, take an individual approach to children. He should be able to interest children, take advantage of the capabilities of each child at work, his prospects. When dealing with children, it is necessary to understand the relationship of children, their inner world. A child entering the world of choreographic knowledge should know that every lesson is mandatory. Leaving training without excuses is impossible due to the peculiarities of the art of choreography. Children cannot cope with the tasks they are facing. It's not even about achieving results, but about the concept of mastering, its development. It is necessary to do the work that he started with good intentions and bring it to the end.

The tendency of children to abandon what they started halfway becomes adult incompetence in the future, so the teacher must build all educational work in accordance with the principle of interest in the team, which is of

fundamental and decisive importance. This is supported by the constant study of new choreographic material (image-to him monand movement, dance combination, dance etiquette, preparation for some event or conducting it, etc.). All this causes positive emotions in children, affects the development of their moral attitude and aesthetic culture. The forms and methods of educational work can be different and depend on the nature and direction of the creative activity of the team. Starting the performance, the baletmaster will tell the children about the character and image of the characters, the motives of their actions, the created history of the performance, everyday life, costumes and traditions. All this should be prepared for children in a language that is understandable to them, and also show colorful pictures, present the material in an emotional and expressive way. Watching special films, listening to music, watching together brings children and the teacher closer together.

A common topic of conversation appears, in which the teacher cleverly and politely directs children to the channel of correct thinking. Discipline education instills organizational skills in the labor process, in which it fosters an active attitude. The teacher in the class evokes respect for general work, develops the ability to subordinate the personality to the public. Conscious discipline is a discipline of internal organization and purposefulness. External discipline creates prerequisites for internal self-education. Children concentrate their mind, attention increases in the classroom, the task given is completed faster and more accurately [3].

Performances of a modern-themed performance encourage meeting interesting people, reading literature, visiting museums and studying new dance materials, creating new choreographic images using examples created by famous masters of choreographic art, for example: dances of the legendary Mukharram Turgunboeva. , " Tanovar", " Munojot", " Pilla", " Ayran " and many other choreographic compositions were the Golden foundation of Uzbek choreography, decorating not only concert halls, but also Ballet Theater scenes [4]. One worthy example was the National Ballet" Tanovar". [5]

Sometimes an image that suddenly appears in the artist's imagination, and then changes over the years in his work. This repetition often impresses with the type of female faces, the proximity to the artist's heart, their originality. This reflection of flattery creates the artist's style. Charm is the world of femininity. The folk song "Tanovar" was composed by A.Kozlovsky, it became such a charm in music. Recorded from Halima Nazirova, it formed the basis of a work for voice and orchestra, and it was performed for the first time

on a concert stage. He sang seven variants of this song to Kozlovsky. Of these, he chose a number of tactics of the same tune and created his own "Tanovar". This work was written by the composer A.Kozlovsky holds a special place in his work, he included in this work all the accumulated wealth of his knowledge of folk tones, rhythms, forms, all the feelings of poetry, the dissolution of everything he knew and loved. In this ballet, he pretended to bequeath his entire fortune to the Uzbek people.

It is useful to see and discuss performances by both professional and amateur teams, concert programs together, and to analyze the group's own concert programs.

The leader is forced to dwell on the pros and cons of the program. It is important to pay attention to everyone, taking into account the individual characteristics of the character. A good word spoken at the right time, support, approval will help in many ways to unravel the ability of the performer. Creative reports, the exchange of experience between teams, the provision of creative assistance to each other carry out a great educational work. The story of meetings with talented creators, their profession, images created in performances has a strong emotional impact on children.

Conclusion. Every day we live, every lesson, rehearsal or concert changes the interests and possibilities of children. Even the smallest features that appear in the learning process cannot be denied. The activity of children in the classroom in the choreographic team depends on the creative initiative of the leader, the desire to lead his students to improve their performance skills and healthy spiritual development.

Creative personality is the most important goal of the entire educational process, aesthetic education. Without it, it is impossible to solve the most important task of the comprehensive and harmonious development of the individual without forming the ability to aesthetic creativity. It turns out that each teacher prepares children for transformative activities through aesthetic education. The head of choreographic groups should communicate with art in children, understand its language, form, develop and strengthen love for it and good taste.

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